

THE PRINCIPAL CRITERIONS OF ASSESSING THE MICRO AND MACRO SKILLS IN READING AND WRITING

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Abstract:

The article investigates the principal criterions of assessing the micro and macro skills in reading and writing.

Key words: reading skills, assessing, macro skills, reading comprehension, conceptual strategies.

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In literate societies, most “normal” children are five or six years old, and some learn to read earlier in the family. Reading is a simple skill. Reading in compulsory language learning is also a skill that teachers expect students to master. Basic, elementary textbooks in a foreign language include the student’s ability to read. Many formal tests use written word as a stimulus for the test taker’s response, and even oral conversations are a process that requires reading for specific tasks. Reading is arguably the most important skill for success in all areas of education, and it remains the most important skill in assessing our ability to speak a common language. To become an effective reader for English learners, two main barriers need to be overcome. The first is that they should be able to master basic bottom-up strategies for processing individual letters, words, and phrases, as well as top-down, conceptual strategies for understanding. The second is that, as part of a top-down approach, second-language learners need to develop appropriate content and formal schemes - background information and cultural experience - to effectively implement these interpretations.

Assessing the ability to read documents does not end with measuring comprehension. Strategic approaches that lead to full understanding are often important parts that need to be included in most of the assessments, especially in an audience that is formative in nature. The inability to comprehend may be related to the need to improve the examiner’s strategy to achieve the No. 1 understanding. For example, an academic technical report may be understandable to a student at the sentence level, but misunderstandings can occur if the student has not used certain strategies to focus on the speech rules of that genre. When considering several types or genres of written texts, components of reading ability, and specific tasks that are widely used in reading assessment, we must not forget the unobserved nature of reading. Apart from observing the learner’s eye movements and page rotation, there is no technology that allows them to “see” a sequence of graphic characters moving from book pages to brain units. Even more bizarre is the notion that it is possible to observe information coming from the brain falling onto a page. Also, once something is read - information is stored in the written text - no technology allows us to empirically measure exactly what is in the brain.

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Each type or genre of written text has its own set of management rules. To effectively process meaning, the reader must know these strategies in advance. The more genres there are in a literacy culture, the more complex the reader's ability to process texts must be. The following genres are used to assess reading ability in the literature:

1. Articles on general interest in academic reading (journals, newspapers, etc.), technical reports (for example, laboratory reports), references to professional journal articles (dictionaries, etc.), textbooks, abstracts, test articles grievances [2,98].

2. Work-related reading messages (e.g., telephone messages) letters / emails (e.g., inter-office) reports (e.g., job evaluations, project reports) tables, labels, signs, announcements forms, applications, inquiries financial documents (invoices, invoices, etc.) references (telephone, office, etc.) manuals, instructions

3. Personal reading letters from newspapers and magazines, e-mails, greetings, invitation messages, notes, list tables recipes, menus, maps, calendar ads, commercials, novels, short stories, jokes, drama, poetry financial documents, questionnaires, medical reports, immigration documents, comics, cartoons [3,65].

It is the learning of reading a text in a compulsory language that allows the reader to distinguish certain schemes. The validity of the evaluation procedure is largely determined by the text genre. For example, if students in an English program for tourism are learning how to interact with clients who need to organize bus trips, then guides, maps, transportation schedules to assess their ability, calendars and other relevant texts.

There are micro and macro skills in language learners skills. In addition to focusing on text genres, reading skills are important in assessing reading ability. The following micro- and macro skills represent a key criterion in assessing reading comprehension.

Main types of designing reading assessment tasks:

1. Perspective reading tasks involve dealing with broader parts of speech: letters, words, punctuation, and other graphemic characters [4, 45].

2. Selective. This category is mainly an artifact of assessment formats. Some typical tasks to determine whether a language recognizes lexical, grammatical, or speech features in a very short section of reading include the tasks we describe, adaptation, correct / incorrect, multiple choices, and so on includes

3. Interactive. Types of interactive reading include a dictionary of a few paragraphs to a few pages or more, in which the reader must interact with the text in a psycholinguistic sense. That is, reading is the process of discussing meaning, the reader brings to the text a set of schemes to understand it, and acceptance is the product of that interaction. Typical genres suitable for interactive reading are anecdotes, short stories and descriptions, excerpts from longer texts, questionnaires, notes, announcements, directions, recipes, and more. The purpose of the interactive task is to identify relevant features (lexical, symbolic, grammatical, and speech) in average short texts in order to preserve the processed information [1,235].

4. Extensive reading refers to more than one page of texts, including professional articles, essays, technical reports, short stories, and books. (It should be noted that reading research usually refers to a longer continuation of speech when speaking of "broad reading," for example, long articles and books that are usually read outside the audience) as opposed to asking for "magnification of small details" is to achieve a global understanding of the text by the reader.

The table shows the relationship between the four types of length, focus, and processing mode. Some learners are already literate in their native language, but in other cases the second language may be the first language they have learned to read. This latter context raises cognitive and sometimes age-related problems that need to be considered

carefully. Literacy assessment is not a simple task Assessment of basic reading skills can be done in a variety of ways.

Centuries ago, writing was one of a kind of skill that was a special field of education or religious scholars and scientists. In ancient times, for “ordinary” people, almost all areas of daily life were done orally. Commercial agreements, documents, legal documents, political and military agreements are written only by specialists who are responsible for providing the language with written word. And now the ability to write has become an integral skill in our global literacy community. Only half a century ago, experts in the field of teaching a second language knew that writing was primarily a basis for recording speech and strengthening the grammatical and lexical features of the language. Now we understand the uniqueness of writing as a skill with unique characteristics and conventions. In developed countries, every educated child learns the basic rules of writing in their native language, but very few people learn to articulate their lives clearly with a logical, well-developed organization that achieves its goal. Evaluating writing is not a simple task. When considering assessing students' writing ability, you should be clear about your goals or criteria as usual.

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